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Undergraduate Students' Perception Of The Use Of Artificial Intelligence In Teaching And Learning In Tertiary Institutions In Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated Undergraduate Students' perception of the use of Artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in tertiary institutions in Delta State. A total of three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design with a sample size of 450 undergraduate students selected from tertiary institutions across the three senatorial zones of Delta State. Proportionate and convenience sampling techniques were used in the selection. The instrument used for data collection was an adapted Global ChatGPT Student Survey, with a reliability coefficient of 0.82. Mean, standard deviation and independent samples t-test were used to analyse the data. The finding revealed that majority of the students use Artificial Intelligence to a very high extent; that majority of the students rate the capabilities of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning to be high; and that students have a high level of satisfaction with the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. No significant gender difference in students' perception of use, capabilities and satisfaction with artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. Among others, the study recommended that artificial intelligence should be integrated into the curriculum of tertiary institutions. This will help provide a proper guidance to the students on how best to use artificial intelligence to enhance their learning experience.

Keywords: Students; Perception; Artificial Intelligence; Tertiary Institutions.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching and learning in most Nigerian tertiary institutions rely on the traditional method of face-to-face lectures, paper-based assessments, and limited access to digital resources. These methods are often characterised by overcrowded classrooms and delayed feedbacks. The cumulative effect of these challenges is a strained educational system that hampers students' academic performance, making it difficult for them to fully engage with their studies and receive the necessary support to succeed. This has created a need for more personalised learning opportunities. One of such opportunities is the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into the educational system.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a computer system that includes human-like processes like learning, adapting, synthesizing, self-correcting, and using data for complex processing tasks. While numerous artificial intelligence solutions rely heavily on programmable algorithms, a subset of these technologies possesses the advanced capability to learn from data patterns and make predictive inferences. Machine learning is software that makes predictions, finds trends, and applies certain patterns that have recently been discovered to situations not covered by their primary architecture (Fahimirad & Kotamjani, 2018). Artificial Intelligence

(AI) is a device or instrument that is commonly used throughout the world. These include certain technologies such as smartphones, the Internet, search engines, various applications, and household appliances. In addition, they are involved in some human-like processes to some extent and can do some complicated teaching and learning tasks in the world.

AI offers viable solutions by automating routine tasks, enabling personalised learning, and supporting data-driven decision-making (Popenici & Kerr, 2017). The global integration of AI in educational systems has opened new avenues for enhancing teaching and learning. Technologies such as intelligent tutoring systems and automated grading have been introduced to personalise education and improve engagement (Hsiao et al., 2018). Artificial intelligence demonstrates considerable potential for application within tertiary institutions by offering continuous, on-demand assistance, personalized tutoring, advanced revision support, and accessibility services. These functions are particularly advantageous for students who require flexible learning opportunities, individualized explanations, or language-related support. Furthermore, AI facilitates the generation of practice exercises, the summarization of complex material, and provides assistance with academic writing tasks, thereby serving as a crucial resource for student learning and self-directed educational activities. In alignment with the growing demand for technological innovation, a significant number of universities in Nigeria have intensified efforts to integrate technology into their traditional pedagogical frameworks (Abubakar et al., 2024). As premier academic institutions, they are committed to adopting strategies that elevate educational standards and better equip students for the challenges of an increasingly digital world. Nonetheless, several challenges persist, including issues surrounding academic integrity due to the potential misuse of AI in coursework and examinations, the danger of excessive reliance on AI that may impede the development of critical thinking skills, and occasional inaccuracies in AI-generated outputs, which could misinform students who lack robust foundational knowledge (Ravselj et al., 2025). Additionally, concerns related to data privacy and security further complicate AI adoption, with many students uncertain about how their personal information is managed. The inability of AI systems to fully comprehend emotional and contextual nuances also restricts their capacity to meet the complex, individualized needs of learners.

In view of the above, students' perceptions regarding integration of AI into the teaching and learning need to be explored. Understanding student perceptions is very crucial, because these perceptions significantly influence learning experiences, technology adoption, and overall academic success (Sanasintani, 2023). Mahyiddin and Amin (2022) found that student attitudes play a pivotal role in the effectiveness of technology adoption in educational settings. User acceptance is key to successful uptake of technological innovations (Davis, 1989). John Biggs highlighted the critical role of student perception within his 3P model (Presage–Process–Product) of teaching and learning (Biggs, 2011). He argued that students' views regarding their learning environment, their self-assessed abilities, and the instructional methods employed significantly shape their learning approaches (Biggs, 1999), which ultimately affect their academic achievements. When students view aspects of the learning environment—such as curriculum content, instructional techniques, assessment styles, available resources, learning context, and support services—positively and have confidence in their capabilities, they are more inclined to engage in deep learning. This approach emphasizes understanding and connecting ideas. Conversely, negative perceptions of the environment or low confidence in their skills often lead students to adopt a surface approach, characterized by rote memorization and minimal effort to meet basic requirements (Biggs, 2011). In educational settings, students' attitudes, experiences, and concerns about technological innovations can significantly influence their readiness to adopt these tools, thereby affecting how thoroughly technology becomes embedded in the learning experience.

Consequently, the current study focuses on assessing undergraduate students' perception of the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The outcome of the study will be beneficial to teachers and policymakers to make informed decisions about adopting and implementing AI technologies in these institutions. Examining these perspectives will allow the study to identify both the opportunities that AI presents. These findings are expected to contribute to the broader academic and practical discourse on AI in education, providing valuable recommendations for how universities can effectively integrate AI into their pedagogical practices.

A growing body of research has explored students' perceptions and attitudes toward the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in educational contexts. Clarke (2025), for instance, conducted an investigation into undergraduate students' perceptions of AI within a Jamaican Higher Education Institution (HEI). Utilizing a quantitative case study design, an online survey was administered to 262 undergraduates, with the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model serving as the study's theoretical underpinning. Descriptive statistics were employed for data analysis, with strict compliance to ethical research standards. The results indicated that while students demonstrated general awareness of AI, they exhibited limited hands-on experience with a variety of AI tools. Although students acknowledged the potential advantages of AI, concerns were raised regarding issues of originality, data privacy, accuracy, and excessive dependence on AI technologies. Participants further emphasized the necessity for enhanced institutional support, advocating for increased training, access to resources, and the provision of clear guidelines on the ethical use of AI. Clarke's study underscores the significant role of prior experiences, ethical apprehensions, and media representations in shaping students' willingness to adopt AI, suggesting that successful AI integration within Jamaican HEIs requires a comprehensive strategy. Such a strategy should include specialized training initiatives, the development of user-friendly AI applications, supportive academic environments, and a proactive approach to addressing ethical challenges. This research offers valuable perspectives to guide the responsible and effective incorporation of AI technologies within higher education institutions.

Moreover, investigations into students' attitudes and experiences with AI have further illuminated the educational benefits of these technologies. Research focusing on AI applications in language classrooms, for example, has demonstrated that students perceive AI tools as highly beneficial for enhancing language learning (Bailey et al., 2021; Sumakul et al., 2020). Similarly, studies examining the use of chatbots within business education reported positive student feedback, with many participants noting improved learning experiences (Chen et al., 2023). Across various disciplines, students largely agreed that AI would significantly influence their academic fields and future professional trajectories (Bisdas et al., 2021; Gong et al., 2019; Sit et al., 2020). Furthermore, a substantial number of students expressed intentions to incorporate AI into their ongoing learning and future professional practices (Bisdas et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2022), reinforcing the view that AI integration is an indispensable element of contemporary university curricula (Abdelwahab et al., 2022; Bisdas et al., 2021; Gong et al., 2019; Yüzbaşıoğlu, 2021).

In view of the above, it can be observed, that various studies have been carried out on students' perception of the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in tertiary institutions. However, there is a paucity of studies in Delta State tertiary institutions. This is the gap that the current explored. Addressing this gap is crucial for understanding the potential impact of AI on educational outcomes in the study area.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How do students perceive the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning?
2. How do students perceive the capabilities of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning?
3. What is the level of students' satisfaction with the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in the study at 0.05 level of significance:

1. No statistically significant difference exists between male and female students regarding their perceptions of the utilization of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning
2. No statistically significant difference exists between male and female students in their perceptions of the capabilities of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning
3. No statistically significant difference exists between male and female students' satisfaction with the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning

METHODS

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. A total of 600 undergraduate students were recruited as participants of the study. The participants were recruited from tertiary institutions across the three senatorial districts of Delta State through a proportionate stratified and convenience sampling techniques. The participants comprise 300 males and 300 females. Proportionate stratified sampling technique was used to determine the number of participants to recruit from tertiary institutions in each of the senatorial districts in the state. Convenience sampling technique was used to identify participants who are available and are willing to participant in the study.

Questionnaire was used to collect data. The questionnaire was adapted from the Global ChatGPT Student Survey, developed by Ravselj et al. (2024). The questionnaire was originally developed to measure students' perception of ChatGPT. However, the researcher adapted it for the purpose of this study because ChatGPT is a common artificial intelligence chatbot. Hence, the questionnaire can be used for the purpose of the study. Items in the questionnaire were structured on a 4-point scale, ranging from 1 for strongly disagree to 4 for strongly agree. As the questionnaire was originally intended for a global audience, which Nigeria is a part, there was no need for revalidation. However, to ascertain if items in the instrument will be fully understood by undergraduate students in the study area, 50 copies of the instrument were administered to students outside the study area but similar to the population. A Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient was used to analyse the data and a coefficient of 0.82 was obtained, which indicate a high reliability.

The data was collected by the researcher with the support of research assistants recruited to help with data collection. The researcher obtained the informed consent of the students, assuring them of confidentiality of their data. The students were also assured that the process is completely voluntary and that they were free to discontinue if and whenever they feel uncomfortable. At the end the exercise, a total of 600 copies of questionnaire were administered and a total of 573 copies was retrieved completely and correctly filled. This indicate 95.5% retrieval rate, which is adequate enough for a descriptive study of this nature. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions at 2.50 benchmark. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: How do students perceive the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning?

Table 1: Mean analysis of how students perceive the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning

S/N	Use of Artificial Intelligence	n	Mean	SD	Remark
1	To what extent do you use Artificial Intelligence in general	573	3.16	0.90	High
How often do you use Artificial Intelligence for the following task					
2	Translating (converting text from one language to another)	573	3.10	0.84	High
3	Professional writing (writing e-mails)	573	3.10	0.81	High
4	Summarizing (generating concise summaries of lengthy texts)	573	3.09	0.85	High
5	Coding assistance (getting assistance with programming)	573	3.03	0.94	High
6	Creative writing (generating stories, poems)	573	3.03	0.90	High
7	Proofreading (receiving feedback on writing)	573	3.02	0.91	High
8	Research assistance (finding information for research papers)	573	3.02	0.93	High
9	Academic writing (writing assignments, research papers)	573	2.99	0.86	High
10	Calculating help (solving mathematical problems)	573	2.98	0.93	High
11	Study assistance (practising for exams)	573	2.97	0.91	High
12	Brainstorming (generating new ideas)	573	2.96	0.92	High
13	Personal assistance (seeking advice on various personal topics)	573	2.93	0.95	High
Grand Mean			3.03	0.90	High
Criterion Mean = 2.50					

Table 1 shows the mean analysis of how students perceive the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. The result shows that the mean ranged from 2.93 to 3.16, with a grand mean of 3.03, indicating a high extent. From the result, majority of the students use Artificial Intelligence to a very high extent. They often use artificial intelligence for various tasks, ranging from translating, professional writing, summarizing to personal assistance.

Research Question 2: *How do students perceive the capabilities of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning?*

Table 2: Mean analysis of how students perceive the capabilities of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning

S/N	Capabilities of Artificial Intelligence	n	Mean	SD	Remark
1	respond in human language.	573	3.06	0.91	High
2	hold a pleasant conversation.	573	3.05	0.92	High
3	understand indications given in human language.	573	3.00	0.96	High
4	provide information efficiently.	573	2.99	0.98	High
5	facilitate online learning (using digital technologies).	573	2.97	0.93	High
6	simplify complex information.	573	2.96	0.99	High
7	facilitate traditional learning (in a classroom).	573	2.92	0.95	High
8	summarize extensive information.	573	2.88	0.97	High
9	facilitate blended (hybrid) learning (a mix of traditional and online learning).	573	2.85	1.02	High
10	provide reliable information.	573	2.80	0.98	High
Grand Mean			2.95	0.96	High

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 2 shows the mean analysis of how students perceive the capabilities of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. The result shows that the mean ranged from 2.80 to 3.06, with a grand mean of 2.95, indicating a high extent. From the result, majority of the students rate the capabilities of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning to be high. They rated that artificial intelligence has the capabilities to respond in human language, hold a pleasant conversation, understand indications given in human language, provide information efficiently, and facilitate online learning.

Research Question 3: *What is the level of students' satisfaction with the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning?*

Table 3: Mean analysis of the level of students' satisfaction with the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning

S/N	Students' Satisfaction with the Use of Artificial Intelligence	n	Mean	SD	Remark
1	I find Artificial Intelligence more useful than Google or other web search engines.	573	2.98	0.96	High
2	It is easier for me to interact with Artificial Intelligence than with my colleagues.	573	2.91	0.96	High
3	I am satisfied with the quality of information provided by Artificial Intelligence.	573	2.86	1.02	High
4	I am satisfied with the accuracy of the information provided by Artificial Intelligence.	573	2.85	0.99	High
5	It is easier for me to interact with Artificial Intelligence than with my professors.	573	2.84	1.00	High
6	I am satisfied with the level of assistance provided by Artificial Intelligence.	573	2.83	0.97	High
7	The information I get from Artificial Intelligence is clearer than the one provided by my professors.	573	2.79	1.02	High
Grand Mean			2.87	0.99	High

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 3 shows the mean analysis of the level of students' satisfaction with the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. The result shows that the mean ranged from 2.79 to 2.98, with a grand mean of 2.87, indicating a high level of satisfaction. From the result, majority of the students find Artificial Intelligence more useful than Google or other web search engines, find it easier to interact with Artificial Intelligence than with my colleagues, are satisfied with the quality of information provided by Artificial Intelligence and are satisfied with the accuracy of the information provided by Artificial Intelligence.

Hypothesis 1: No statistically significant difference exists between male and female students regarding their perceptions of the utilization of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning

Table 4: t-test comparison of male and female students' perception of the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning

Group	n	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value	Remark
Male	257	3.06	0.57				
Female	316	3.00	0.71	571	1.09	0.27	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 4 shows an independent samples t-test, which was used to compare male and female students' perception of the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. The result shows that male students ($m = 3.06$) had a higher perception of the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning than their female counterparts ($f = 3.00$). The null hypothesis is however, accepted, $t(571) = 1.09$, $p > 0.05$ level of significance. This means that No statistically significant difference exists between male and female students regarding their perceptions of the utilization of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning.

Hypothesis 2: No statistically significant difference exists between male and female students in their perceptions of the capabilities of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning

Table 5: t-test comparison of male and female students' perception of the capabilities of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning

Group	n	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value	Remark
Male	257	2.92	0.71				
Female	316	2.97	0.71	571	0.80	0.43	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 5 shows an independent samples t-test, which was used to compare male and female students' perception of the capabilities of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. The result shows that female students ($f = 2.97$) had a higher perception of the capabilities of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning than their male counterparts ($m = 2.92$). The null hypothesis is however, accepted, $t(571) = 0.80$, $p > 0.05$ level of significance. This means that no statistically significant difference exists between male and female students in their perceptions of the capabilities of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning.

Hypothesis 3: No statistically significant difference exists between male and female students' satisfaction with the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning

Table 6: t-test comparison of male and female students' satisfaction with the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning

Group	n	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value	Remark
Male	257	2.84	0.70				
Female	316	2.89	0.72	571	0.79	0.43	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 6 shows an independent samples t-test, which was used to compare male and female students' satisfaction with the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. The result shows that female students ($f = 2.89$) had a higher satisfaction with the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning than their male counterparts ($m = 2.84$). The null hypothesis is however, accepted, $t(571) = 0.79$, $p > 0.05$ level of significance. This means that no statistically significant difference exists between male and female students' satisfaction with the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning.

DISCUSSIONS

The finding revealed that majority of the students use Artificial Intelligence to a very high extent. They often use artificial intelligence for various tasks such as translating, professional writing, summarizing, coding assistance, creative writing and proofreading. Other tasks include research assistance, academic writing, calculating help, study assistance, brainstorming and personal assistance. A corresponding hypothesis showed that No statistically significant difference exists between male and female students regarding their perceptions of the utilization of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. This finding suggests revolution in digital transformation and increase appreciation of artificial intelligence. Students are becoming more aware of the artificial intelligence and are using it to enhance their learning experience. This finding agrees with Ravselj, et al. (2025), who in their study of students' Higher education students' perceptions of ChatGPT found that students generally accepted that they use artificial intelligence for a range of tasks to enhance their learning experience, and that significantly lower scores for usage were achieved by males. The finding also corroborates the finding of Chan and Hu's (2023) finding, which revealed that artificial intelligence can be used for a range of tasks to enhance personalized learning across diverse academic areas. The finding also found that majority of the students rate the capabilities of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning to be high. Majority of the students rated that artificial intelligence has the capabilities to respond in human language, hold a pleasant conversation, understand indications given in human language, provide information efficiently and facilitate online learning. They also agreed that artificial intelligence has the capabilities to simplify complex information, facilitate traditional learning, summarize extensive information, facilitate blended, learning and provide reliable information. A corresponding hypothesis revealed that no significant difference exists between male and female students' perception of the capabilities of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. This finding suggests that artificial intelligence is usual friendly and can easily be navigated by the students to enhance their learning experience. This finding agrees with Ravselj, et al. (2025), who in their study of students' Higher education students' perceptions of ChatGPT found that students were generally aware of AI's capabilities to enhance their learning experience, and that gender had only minor implications for student perceptions of AI's capabilities. It is however, at variance with the findings of Mai et al. (2024), who noted similar concerns about the reliability and classroom integration of AI tools.

The finding further revealed that students have a high level of satisfaction with the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. Majority of the students find artificial intelligence more useful than Google or other web search engines, find it easier to interact with artificial intelligence than with my colleague, satisfied with the quality of information provided by artificial intelligence and satisfied with the accuracy of the information provided by artificial intelligence. They also find it easier to interact with artificial intelligence than with their professors, satisfied with the level of assistance provided by artificial intelligence and agreed that the information they get from artificial intelligence is clearer than the one provided by my professors. A corresponding hypothesis showed that no statistically significant difference exists between male and female students' satisfaction with the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. This finding is not farfetched. For the fact that the students already reported using artificial intelligence with its reported easy to use capabilities, there is every tendency that the students will be satisfied with using it to enhance their learning experience. This finding agrees with Ravselj, et al. (2025), who in their study of students' Higher education students' perceptions of ChatGPT found that students were generally satisfied with AI's usefulness and assistance, but that male students reported higher levels of satisfaction than their female counterparts. The finding is however, at variance with Schepman and Rodway (2023), who reported more positive AI attitudes in men, which may be due to greater comfort with technology.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the finding of the study, it can be concluded that indeed, undergraduate Students' use Artificial intelligence in teaching for enhancing their learning experience to a high extent. They have positive perception of the capabilities and are satisfied with the overall use of artificial intelligence for enhancing their learning experience. Hence, it is noteworthy that artificial intelligence has come to stay as far as the

educational system is concerned. Students find it very useful in a wide range of educational tasks. The perception of the students towards the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning cut across their gender, with male and female having almost similar disposition. In view of this conclusion, the following recommendations have been made:

1. Artificial intelligence should be integrated into the curriculum of tertiary institutions. This will help provide a proper guidance to the students on how best to use artificial intelligence to enhance their learning experience
2. The students should be adequately supervised by lectures and school management on how best to maximize its capabilities
3. Management of tertiary institutions to should leverage on the high satisfaction of students towards the use of artificial intelligence to create a balance between its application and human interaction.

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